

Mapping Microstructure: Manifold Construction for Accelerated Materials Exploration

Dissertation

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Abstract

The development of new materials is a historically slow process, often taking decades to go from discovery to deployment. This is in part due to the gradual, iterative nature of materials development, combining “guess-and-check” approaches with institutional knowledge, as well as the decidedly high-dimensional and non-linear relationships between processing conditions, material states, and resultant performance. Therefore, new analysis methods must be developed to meet the increased demands of material requirements, novel design spaces, and advanced characterization techniques. This work outlines a mathematical framework to formalize these hyper-dimensional relationships, using the stochastic representation of microstructure and establishing microstructure distance metrics as a way to understand the distributions of microstructure images within one state, as well as between states in the domain as a whole. By mapping the relationships between material processing parameters and the resulting microstructures, a navigable domain, referred to as the material manifold, can be constructed and utilized to improve the value of exploratory investigations and optimization efforts. This methodology is demonstrated through the stochastic simulation of two-phase microstructures across a design space, establishing quantitative representations of material states to understand the reciprocal nature of process and structure. Assessments on the quality of representations, characteristics of the material domain, and integration with neural network-based image generators were completed to explore the potential for manifold

learning in materials science. The tools developed can be harnessed for automated materials discovery, as well as used to complement the ever-growing application of statistical and machine learning methods with materials science.

To Molybdenum

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Chapter 1: Introduction

The development of new materials is a fundamentally iterative process, with early metallurgical practices revolving around ad-hoc methods like “heat it and beat it” or “cook and look” to gradually refine manufacturing techniques. It is only in the last century or so with the advent of microscopy that metallurgy has transitioned from a craft to a science and developed into the field of materials science [2]. Much of the challenge in modern materials development is due to the complex relationships between processing conditions and resultant properties, and slow exploration leaves new materials systems at risk of stagnating and falling into the developmental “Valley of Death” (VoD) [3]. In an attempt to accelerate the development process, integrated computational materials engineering (ICME) methodologies like microstructure sensitive design (MSD) [4] and microstructure informatics (MI) [5] are being developed to establish data-driven approaches to the mapping of the processing-structure-property relationships (PSPRs). A key strategy for successful technology development proposed by the National Research Council (NRC) is through “quick, iterative development cycles”, with quantifiable measurements providing feedback information on the impact of developmental changes [3]. In order to enable rapid development of new materials through iterative design processes, data-driven practices and quantitative analysis can be used to formalize the relationships between the processing and structure domains, defining a mapping between these domains - termed the material manifold.

For this purpose, we define the notion of *navigability* on the material manifold as the ability to make predictable changes between the processing and structure domains within a full feedback control loop. This enables iterative development and optimization to reach a target material structure with desired properties and performance, intuitively following the approach of a process design engineer. *Navigability* within a material system enables sequential experimental iterations to be taken in informative and/or meaningful directions, more quickly converging on an optimized solution to tune material structures with respect to processing conditions and resultant properties.

This work utilizes two concepts for establishing functional mappings between the processing and structure domains to enable informative, quantitative feedback for rapid material development: material state descriptors and the manifold hypothesis. The stochastic representation of microstructure allows us to establish material state descriptors by defining “microstructure” as a generating process/random variable controlled by processing conditions, rather than the more traditional interpretation of “microstructure” as an image. [6]. Paired with the manifold hypothesis, which asserts that there exists some latent domain “described by a function of only a few underlying parameters” [7], the relationship between processing conditions and potential microstructure states can be mapped out across the design space, constructing the material manifold.

We hypothesize that the stochastic representation of microstructure allows for a navigable mapping between material processing conditions and resulting microstructure. We will test this hypothesis by comparing the (1) dimensionality, (2) invertibility, and (3) stability of different descriptor methods to determine the stochastic representation’s ability to capture the controlling features of the underlying process.

1.1 Context

1.1.1 Materials Development

Whether in historical, craft-based disciplines like blacksmithing, or in modern, scientific-based disciplines like metallurgy, new materials having more desirable properties are developed as part of an iterative process based on the practitioner's inherent, accumulated knowledge of the design space, making adjustments in processing conditions to create the final component. For example, a blacksmith making horseshoes understands the scope of their design space with respect to horseshoe size, strength, etc., and is able to adjust their smithing procedure to manufacture different horseshoes for a draft workhorse versus a race horse. Modern metallurgy formalizes many of these notions, focusing on how processing and structure relate to properties and performance. Modern practitioners have the same type of inherent understanding on the scope of the materials design space and how processing adjustments lead to structural changes. We want to develop tangible, mathematical representations of that paired understanding of processing and structure domains that can be effectively harnessed to accelerate the development of new materials.

For example, in developing a new material with precipitate particles in a polycrystalline matrix, a practitioner hypothesizes that some desirable property (e.g. hardness, yield strength) changes with respect to precipitate behaviour (size/distribution). In testing this hypothesis, various heat treatment processes are tested to determine the impact of processing variables (time, temperature, cooling rate) on structural features (grain size, precipitate size). When measuring property responses, the practitioner determines that some combination of smaller grain size and larger precipitates is needed to reach the desired mechanical response and determines a potential heat treatment pathway that could lead to this microstructure. Upon testing this heat treatment, the practitioner can measure the final microstructural features and resultant properties to determine if the needed material has

Figure 1.1: Iterative materials development process

been developed, or alternatively adjust the process according to an inverse ICME model built using the obtained material system knowledge.

1.1.2 Conceptualizing Microstructure

Despite being a foundational concept for materials science and engineering, there is no universally agreed upon definition for microstructure. One potential difficulty in defining microstructure lies in the fact that each practitioner interacts with “microstructure” in a different manner and thus forms a different relationship with the concept based on their

specific area of focus. Since the 1800s, microstructure most often meant “what you see with a microscope” [8]. For scientists mostly engaged in characterization this is still the most useful working definition. This view contrasts strongly with the concept of microstructure prevalent within the processing community, where structure is not interpreted as a specific arrangement of features but rather as set of descriptors summarizing the desired features. For example, a microscopist may think of the microstructure of a material class as a set of micrographs taken over a large area from a sample and their understanding of common features present in this set of images. Alternatively, a materials design engineer may have a latent, conceptual understanding of a microstructure class based on a distribution of microstructural features and how they impact a resulting design constraint/physical property.

Each practitioner develops an inherent mental picture of the structure that is most useful to their area of practice. The ability of the human brain to make latent connections comes from our ability to abstract information from complex data and store and manipulate a simpler representation of this data. These abstract understandings of microstructure are analogous to the latent space of neural networks/autoencoders, and is the concept we are trying to establish with the material manifold. While a microstructure expert may be able to recognize different classes of microstructure and visually distinguish between similar structures, there is a need for a rigorous, mathematical definition of microstructure that is agnostic of an individual’s point-of-view in order to bridge the gap across fields/disciplines. Figure 1.2 shows an example of how two different materials scientists may conceptualize the microstructure from a sample billet of material. It is in service of reconciling these inherent understandings of across disciplines, between process design engineers, materials scientists, and characterization experts, that we wish to develop rigorous methods for describing materials design and state spaces.

Figure 1.2: Conceptualizing microstructure as a microscopist versus materials design engineer.

1.2 Motivation

As material performance requirements and operating environments become increasingly extreme, it is of critical importance that our analysis tools and material development methodologies evolve alongside them to efficiently explore these complex domains. The decidedly high-dimensional and non-linear relationships between processing and structure serve to further increase the complexity of these systems. Additionally, with the adoption of machine learning methods into materials science, the representations of data and domains are becoming increasingly high-dimensional. There is a need for new methods to learn to interpret this type of data, extracting features of greatest importance and disentangling latent variables [9].

The notion of materials domains existing on a latent, manifold space has been established and utilized in materials science. Beyond the practitioner’s intuitive understanding from Section 1.1.2, methods like DREAM.3D calculate feature distributions on microstructure samples that can then be used to synthesize new microstructures [10]. That set of feature distributions represents a reduced-order, latent representation of a materials domain. The Air Force Research Laboratory’s Autonomous Research System (ARES) is another successful approach to not only extracting a latent manifold, but implementing said manifold with autonomous experimentation tools [11]. ARES is able to synthesize material samples, measure properties with *in situ* characterization to define a material state manifold, and then navigate along that learned manifold with dynamic sampling strategies to inform future experiments. This style of dynamic sampling has also proven useful in other areas of materials science, such as in microscopy with the development of a supervised learning based algorithm for dynamic sampling (SLADS), wherein machine learning tools can be integrated with imaging applications to sparsely sample image fields and reconstruct full-resolution images [12]. This approach to data collection enables a reduction in computational cost and time intensive procedures, pushing the envelope of materials development further and faster. As a more traditional example, the Iron-Carbon phase diagram represents a manifold understanding of a material system for equilibrium material states, as defined by the elemental composition of an alloy [13]. Each corresponding point on the phase diagram has associated compositional parameters and material structure. We as materials scientists can harness the manifold hypothesis to establish lower-dimensional representations of the material state space as defined by a handful of parameters [7] - oftentimes the material processing parameters. With the help of the quantitative representation of microstructure, a manifold can be learned to explore the relationship between processing and structure and eventually establish connections to properties in the form of property response landscapes.

Additionally, as materials systems evolve and become more complicated, there is a greater need to remove the human element from development and experimentation, as the number of processing parameters and system complexity increases beyond the ability of intuitive understanding. This necessitates the integration of automated experimentation tools, like Bayesian optimization [14, 15] and active learning [16], to speed up the exploration of these design spaces. These tools can be used to enable autonomous, high-throughput, “on-the-fly” experimentation [17, 18]. Even with integration with automated experimentation, the scope of the optimization landscape must be tractable to be efficiently explored. Well-posed forward and inverse models are needed for integration with ICME models. However, a degree of flexibility is needed for tools to be practically implemented into materials development and manufacturing processes. While the material state space is well known for equilibrium states (e.g. phase diagrams), it must additionally be expanded to far-from-equilibrium systems, such as is seen in additive manufacturing due to the rapid solidification of materials.

1.2.1 Materials Domain Exploration

By way of an analogous concept, one might make a comparison between this type of materials domain exploration to the early mapping of the Earth. Figure 1.3 shows an example of different maps created by humans over the course of the past two millennia [1]. Map 1.3a shows an example of a very early map, created around 200BCE, in which the African, European, and Asian continents can be made out, albeit not quite appearing as we know them today. Important characteristic features, like the transition points between continents (similar to material transitions like phase transformations) are mapped out, but the absolute sizes/shapes of the continents are not correct. Taking a step forward 1500 years, the Mercator projection, Figure 1.3b, shows a new understanding of the map of the world. The “Old World” continents are much better mapped out as we know them today,

and the previously inaccessible “New World” continents have been discovered, but are not yet accurately represented. Additionally, the development of a new mathematical framework for understanding the domain has been established in the Mercator projection itself. Taking an additional step forward, the Double Hemisphere projection shown in Figure 1.3c shows a complete map much closer to the world as we know it. At this stage, a stereographic projection of the globe has been established to most clearly define the continents, and the New World has been explored thoroughly enough to match our modern projections. Additional stages beyond this can be established today, with the introduction of satellite imaging or other techniques like LIDAR scanning to layer on new information like elevation mapping.

One could argue that in terms of materials exploration, we are in the Mercator projection stages of exploration. Well-behaved, equilibrium systems have been explored (Old World), and we have knowledge of non-equilibrium systems (New World), but have not yet fully mapped out these difficult-to-explore regions. We are beyond the stages where the boundaries of the maps are surrounded with drawings of sea dragons and monsters, but not yet able to fully harness these domains to develop advanced materials.

(a) Eratosthenes, ~200 BCE

(b) Mercator Projection, 1569

(c) Dunn's Double Hemisphere, 1794

Figure 1.3: Examples of maps from Wikipedia's History of Cartography [1]

Figure 1.4: Annotated Mercator projection with materials domain exploration analogy.

1.3 Background

1.3.1 Microstructure as a Stochastic Process

A foundational concept for understanding microstructure’s role in the PSPR is treating microstructure as a stochastic process [6]. In this definition, “microstructure” is a stochastic process (i.e. probability distribution) of “essentially equivalent” microstructure realizations sampled independently and identically distributed (iid) from the stochastic process. This notion is revised in this dissertation to instead define **material states** as a stochastic process - with microstructure being one method to represent material state information. The stochastic, generating process is referred to as ‘big M ’ or the ‘ M -state’, and individual realizations within one M -state are known as ‘little m ’s’ or ‘ m -instances’. This M/m representation of materials states and microstructure can be thought of as the difference in ‘microstructure as an image’ vs. ‘microstructure as a description of the state of a material,’ with the former being the m -instances and the latter being the M -state. This notion is similar in spirit to the distinction between a “sample” and “specimen” as defined by Williams et al. with respect to transmission electron microscopy sample preparation [19]. While the term “microstructure” is multifaceted and can take on many meanings, it is often used to refer to an image. From here, we use representative images and the term “microstructure” to mean a m -instance of a M -material state, or alternatively and interchangeably to mean the set of m -instances used to describe a M -state when used in that context. The M/m concept is not novel to this work, however it has mainly been used to describe distributions of m -instances within one M -state or to compare discrete classifications of M -states [6]. This work will expand it to allow for comparisons of M -states across a continuum of states along the \mathcal{M} -manifold.

One (admittedly large) liberty this work takes is to assume that there is no stochasticity in the processing conditions themselves, and all stochastic effects come from the generating process itself. This assumption is unrealistic in practice, as real manufacturing processes

Figure 1.5: Microstructure as a stochastic process.

will have variation in their true conditions due to a wide range of potential factors, from humidity in the air, to fluctuations in temperature, to what the operator ate for lunch that day. The idealistic simulated microstructures used in this work contain no such fluctuations, but this manifold methodology has been proposed in such a way that it could be used to assess the degree of these stochastic processing effects to determine their impact on the final material state.

1.3.2 Processing-Microstructure-Property Relationship and the Need for Multi-scale Representations

The processing-structure-property relationship (PSPR) is a fundamental concept in materials science. Being able to harness the linkage between material processing, its impact on the resulting microstructure, and the property response of these materials, is a powerful tool for microstructure sensitive design (MSD) [4]. Under this methodology, the material domain, design space, and resultant properties are explored with respect to the microstructure. The relationship between processing and properties is difficult to determine directly

but can be understood by relating processing to microstructure and microstructure to properties [20], as shown in Figure 1.6. The processing-structure-property relationship requires a complete description from the microstructure to be able to understand how properties relate to processing conditions.

Figure 1.6: Processing-structure-property relationship triangle.

As of today, this “microstructure bridge” is a primarily academic construct, but increasing complexities in the processing domains and material performance requirements necessitate the development of tools to explore their relationship to microstructure. In practical engineering and historical contexts, materials were explored, developed, and defined by their properties with no insight into microstructure, either because the characterization tools did not exist, or the quantification methods did not allow for microstructure descriptors to be integrated with engineering design. The quantitative representation of microstructure allows for materials state descriptors to be explicitly defined on characterizations of microstructure features.

1.3.3 Quantitative Representation of Microstructure

Microstructure is described by Fullwood et al. as the “myriad features of internal structure of heterogeneous materials across length scales ranging from the atomic through the mesoscale to approaching the macroscale” [4]. As the prefix “micro” indicates, we are usually focused on the microscopic structure, but in the case of components having compositional or processing gradients, important microstructural features can extend well beyond the millimeter length scale. Microstructure quantification and reduced-order representations of microstructure are needed to understand PSPR [21].

Three commonly used approaches for the quantitative representation of microstructure (QRM) are: (1) the explicit calculation of feature distributions [5, 22, 23], (2) the implicit representation of features using reduced-order models [24, 25, 26], and (3) machine learning featurization [27, 28, 29]. At their core, methods (1) and (2) are two sides of the same coin, calculating reduced-order representations of microstructural features, just with different levels of human interaction.

Table 1.1: Microstructure Representation Methods

	Explicit	Implicit	Machine Learning
Pros	Well-defined Highly-controllable	Physically-meaningful Smaller datasets	Fast
Cons	Expert knowledge Pre-processing	Expert knowledge	Black box Large datasets

1.4 Dissertation Outline

This work is divided into 6 chapters, guiding the reader through the establishment of the Material Manifold as a concept, different quantitative methods to approximate the manifold, and integration of the manifold learning approach with machine learning and statistical tools.

Chapter 2 describes the fundamental rules and regulations established for developing the concept of the material manifold. Chapter 3 outlines an approach to mapping out the manifold across a materials domain using different microstructure descriptors and discusses the variations in result for those methods. Chapter 4 shows an alternative approach utilizing novel deep learning/neural network architectures as a way to extract the material manifold, harness the network’s latent space for information extraction and microstructure generation, and discusses the challenges associated with applying machine learning to materials science. Chapter 5 details a statistical test built on top of the manifold framework that can be used to understand properties of the manifold, microstructure descriptors, and assess the quality of ML-based surrogate models for microstructure generation. Chapter 6 concludes the work with a summarization of the successes and failures within this thesis and outlines potential future directions to be passed down to interested readers.

Chapter 2: The Material Manifold

The fundamental contribution of this work revolves around the construction of a material state manifold, or a low-dimensional domain on which each point represents a unique material state. The material manifold is both a conceptual framework to visualize and analyze the variety of material states that exist in a material system [30], as well as a mathematical object that establishes properties needed for an iterative mapping between process and structure [31, 5]. The manifold itself represents a continuum of all possible material states, spanning the design space for a given range of composition and processing conditions. While the concept of a manifold embedding has already been adopted into the field of materials science and machine learning [32, 33], this work formalizes the requirements of quantitative descriptors needed to be applied to this type of analysis.

2.0.1 Defining Microstructure as a Function of Processing

Colloquially, materials scientists are known to say phrases like “microstructure is a function of processing”. However, in our context, what they mean is that the material state is a function of processing, and that microstructure information derived from characterization methods are indicators or descriptors of the material state. Furthermore, characterization datasets or images are often analyzed so that they become formal quantitative descriptors of the material state, as demonstrated later in this writing.

To formalize this notion in this dissertation, Θ will be used to represent the processing domain, and M to represent the material state domain. In defining the forward and inverse models, the forward mapping, $f : \Theta \rightarrow M$, describes microstructure as a function of processing. The inverse mapping, $g : M \rightarrow \Theta$, describes the recovery of parameters as part of that feedback loop. Figure 2.1 shows a diagram of the feedback loop, with one complete cycle consisting of $g(f(\Theta)) = \Theta$.

Figure 2.1: Invertible mapping between the processing and structure domains.

While there are many potential ways to parameterize material states, we choose to do so based off of the processing conditions, as this is the domain that we have control over, separating out Θ as our *controllable* domain, and M as our *observable* domain. This parameterization comes with the caveat that we are assuming a bijective mapping between process and microstructure, where there is a one-to-one correspondence between processing conditions and material states. In practice, this caveat may not always be the case, and is further discussed in later chapters. This restriction is necessary for treating materials development as an inverse problem, where we are able to reduce the forward model from a many-to-one relationship to a one-to-one relationship through the stochastic representation of microstructure.

2.1 The Material Manifold

The material manifold, \mathcal{M} , is parameterized by the collection of all possible processing parameter sets in Θ , where θ represents a unique set of processing parameters and M^θ is

the M -state of material state generated from that process. This definition hinges on the interpretation that different processing conditions result in different material states [34].

$$\mathcal{M} = \{M^\theta : \theta \in \Theta\} \quad (2.1)$$

The material processing parameter domain, Θ , is defined by the controlling parameters of the material system. The dataset consists of m -instances generated from a random process defined over Θ and parameterized by $\theta = (\alpha, \beta)$, where α and β are generic parameters and θ is a unique set of processing parameters. m -instances are the *iid* realizations of states from the M^θ -state, having unique spatial/deterministic information inherent from the stochasticity of the generating process. Figure 2.2 shows a unique M^θ -state from the surface of the manifold and the corresponding set of m -instances used to establish the inherent stochastic variation that exists within the distribution of M^θ . The microstructure images used in this chapter are spinodal decomposition microstructures, described in Section 3.1.1.

$$m_i^\theta \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} M^\theta \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.2: Schematic manifold and distribution of m -instances within a M^θ -state

Figure 2.3 shows a schematic \mathcal{M} -manifold highlighting three different M^θ -states: two represented by similar microstructures (M^1, M^2) that exist close to each other on the manifold and one having a different microstructure state (M^3) further away on the manifold.

Figure 2.3: Schematic manifold and M^θ -states with corresponding sets of m -instances.

2.1.1 The Stochastic Representation of Microstructure and Microstructure Distance Metrics

In understanding microstructure as a stochastic process, m -instances are sampled from M -state distributions. Microstructure descriptors can be established for which equivalent microstructures have equivalent descriptors, within some acceptable tolerance. These microstructure descriptors serve to capture stochasticity of the generating process, as well as the stochasticity of the microstructure descriptor itself, detailing M -state information from

sets of m -instances. For any arbitrary microstructure descriptor, a distance metric can be computed to calculate the degree of similarity between m -instances, or eventually the distances between distributions of M -states. In this section, analysis will be shown using the two-point correlation function as a descriptor due to its relative familiarity in the field of materials science. Specifics on how calculations were completed will be shown in the later Section 3.1.3.

In order to learn information on M -states, microstructure descriptors, D , can be calculated on individual m -instances to return descriptor vectors upon which distance calculations can be performed. Various approaches to calculating microstructure distance metrics have been established [35], however this work defines the metric descriptor distance (MDD), d , as the p -Minkowski norm between descriptor vectors, shown in Equation 2.3. For this work, p was chosen to be 1, following the analysis done by Sundararaghavan et al. [32] that showed the tendency of higher p -Minkowski distances to over-estimate the dimensionality of systems.

$$d(m^1, m^2) = \left(\sum_i |D_i^1 - D_i^2|^p \right)^{1/p} \tag{2.3}$$

Multidimensional scaling (MDS), a non-linear dimensionality reduction technique, can be used to visualize the similarities between m -instances sampled from a given M -state by determining the Cartesian coordinates associated with each data point using the pairwise metric distance values between all samples within a population [36]. Figure 2.4a shows an example of how a set of m -instances are distributed within one M -state using MDS. Kernel density estimation (KDE) is used to visualize the distribution of samples within a M -state.

Figure 2.4: (a) MDS projection of m -instances within a M -state and corresponding (b) pairwise metric descriptor distances array used to determine MDS positions.

2.2 Moving from Local to Global Manifold Relationships

When expanding the analysis from individual M -states to sets of M -states across the manifold, interest shifts from comparing individual m -instances to comparing M -states. While the underlying M^θ stochastic process is unknowable, it can be approximated as \hat{M}^θ from the information available to us - sets of m -instances. While there are many potential choices for approximating M -states and establishing distance metrics between distributions, such as the Earth-Mover/Wasserstein distance used by Miley et al. [37], for simplicities sake, this work will approximate the M -state information as the average descriptor for a set of m -instances and maintain the p-Minkowski-based MDD to calculate distances between material states. Equation 2.4 shows this method for estimating a descriptor of the M -state, \hat{M}^θ :

$$\hat{M}^\theta \approx \bar{D}^\theta = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n D(m_j^\theta) \quad (2.4)$$

where \bar{D}^θ is the average descriptor vector calculated on a set of m -instances. Figure 2.5 shows an example of two neighboring M -states including their respective distributions of m -instances in comparison to one another.

Figure 2.5: MDS projection of two neighboring M -states and their distributions of m -instances.

Establishing distance metrics between m -instances and M -states is necessary for understanding microstructure as a stochastic process [38]. While distances between M -states can be calculated based off of their θ parameters and may offer some semblance of how similar you expect two M -states to be, those distances may not be informative of how microstructures exist on the manifold. There is no sense of variation within one M -state, so it is not

possible to assert questions like “what is the weakest state that exists within this population?”. Additionally, the relationship between θ -parameter and M -state may not always be linear. Over the range of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, there may be areas of the domain where a small change in θ -parameter leads to a relatively larger change in the M -state, defining regions of stability/instability. However, that information can only be captured through measurements on the resultant M -states.

In understanding the full span of the \mathcal{M} -manifold for the entire family of M -states within the processing domain, manifold assessment can be done on local comparisons between m -instances, regional comparisons between neighborhoods of similar M -states, and global assessments on all M -states in the domain. Figure 2.6 shows manifold projection visualizations of these three windows, using the MDS projection for local assessment, and principal component analysis (PCA) to visualize the relationships between M -states using their \hat{M} -approximations for regional and global families of data. PCA and the manifold visualization techniques are described in detail in Section 3.2.4.

Figure 2.6: Expanding manifold analysis from local to regional to global relationships.

2.3 Properties of the Material Manifold

As presented in the introduction, the three properties used to assess the navigability of the manifold mapping between processing and structure domains are the dimensionality, invertibility, and stability. All three of these notions work to compliment one another in order to establish the network of M -states across the \mathcal{M} -manifold.

Dimensionality:

The dimensionality, or more specifically, the intrinsic dimensionality of our material system is of great interest in determining the minimum number of parameters needed to define the manifold - thereby reducing the complexity in future analysis and application tasks. The intrinsic dimensionality is the number of controlling dimensions required to describe a system space.

The dimensionality assessment is performed to determine if the microstructure representations are capturing information on the underlying materials processes, not the aleatoric noise that occurs due to the stochastic nature of sampling multiple microstructure realizations at each M -state. This test is completed by verifying that the mapping from the processing domain, Θ , to the structure domain, M , is dimensionality-preserving - or that Θ and M both exist in \mathbb{R}^n .

Invertibility:

The invertibility assessment is performed to validate that the chosen microstructure descriptors are capturing salient information on the material states and microstructural features present within the m -instances in such a way that their corresponding θ -parameters can be recovered.

Stability:

The stability of the \mathcal{M} -manifold is used to assert that a small change in the input domain (processing) results in a small change in the co-domain (structure). Ideally, as the \hat{M} -approximations are calculated, their representations converge onto a smooth manifold with properly-defined neighboring M -states. This allows for improved invertibility and the greatest degree of dimensionality reduction possible to establish the minimum number of parameters needed to define the domain.

In conclusion, these three properties are all inherently linked - one cannot necessarily exist without the others - and by assessing all three of these properties we can work to establish a meaningful low-dimensional representation of the \mathcal{M} -manifold that can be integrated with the manifold hypothesis.

2.4 Conclusions

Microstructure mapping to establish domain knowledge on the material manifold is important for developing advanced tool sets for exploring novel material systems and domains. By establishing quantitative representations of the domain to be explored, development can be accelerated through rapid, iterative cycles, decreasing the risk and cost associated with exploring new material systems. The material manifold seeks to explore the processing-structure relationships using a combination of material state descriptors and the manifold hypothesis to establish a low-dimensional mapping of the material system.

Further thought and care must be put towards implementing the material manifold hypothesis in more challenging material systems, such as the case where there is not a one-to-one mapping between material processing conditions and resultant structure. In practice, there are situations where multiple different processing pathways can lead to an identical material state. In this case, M -state descriptors must be shifted to include information on the

entire trajectory of the material evolution. This can be difficult to do, necessitating in-situ measurements and data that may not always be accessible. However, if it can be achieved, decisions like “what is the fastest way I can make this material?” can be made. An additional layer of complexity occurs when materials have non-uniform microstructure across the component-scale, like in cast components that have over-aged microstructures at their core in comparison to quicker-cooling external regions. In this case, M -state descriptors must be performed in a hierarchical nature to capture the span of information across the component.

Chapter 3: Quantitative Representation of Microstructure

The primary method by which this dissertation seeks to uncover the underlying \mathcal{M} -manifold is through the quantitative representation of microstructure (QRM) to define stochastic approximations of material state descriptors. While quantitative analysis of microstructures and microstructural features has been around for decades, with techniques ranging from morphological descriptors [39], to stereology [40], to more recent reduced-order approaches [41, 42], and into machine-learning based methods [43], this chapter focuses on the use of mathematically-derived reduced-order models.

This chapter will utilize phase-field simulated microstructures across a defined processing domain to test the stochastic representation of microstructure’s ability to extract a low-dimensional representation of the latent material manifold.

3.1 Material System and Dataset Generation

3.1.1 Spinodal Decomposition Phase Field Simulations

The material domain explored in this work is a representation of phase separation mechanism of spinodal decomposition in two-phase material systems. This is a thermodynamic process by which complex microstructures are generated when a liquid melt is quenched to form a solid having a composition inside the spinodal region, leading to spontaneous phase separation. This quenching process and resulting microstructure is accurately represented by numerically solving using Equation 3.1, the Cahn-Hilliard equation [44, 45]:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D\nabla^2(c^3 - c - \kappa\nabla^2 c) \quad (3.1)$$

where c is the local relative concentration of the binary system components, D is the diffusivity, and κ is the atomic scale interaction length. In this case, κ acts as a proxy for interfacial energy, wherein larger values of κ correspond to a greater energy penalty for having a boundary between phases, leading to fewer, larger particles. The initial stages of separation are highly dependent on the volume fraction, η , which controls the mean value of Gaussian random noise field and thus the local concentration, c , across the spatial realization of microstructure.

The phase-field simulations were run using a C++ finite element difference solver under the conditions of a symmetric double-well free energy potential, assuming fully-coherent interfaces between phases. Diffusivity was fixed for all simulations, and simulations were run for the same time-scale for $t \in [0, T]$. Final time T was predetermined as the length of time needed for microstructure state to remain static over a given Δt . Microstructure simulations were generated on a 2D square grid with size 256×256 pixels for dimensionless spatial and temporal parameters and periodic boundary conditions over all boundaries of the domain. Images are grayscale with uint8 bit depth. The simulations were controlled by three parameters: η , κ , and ξ . Volume fraction, η , and interfacial energy, κ , serve as a proxy for material composition and processing conditions to define the materials process, θ . θ -parameters were chosen by uniformly sampling for η in the range $[-0.25, 0.25]$ and κ in the range $[0.25, 0.75]$. ξ represents the initial state and was a random integer in the range of int64 used to seed a Gaussian noise field in the 256×256 image domain.

Microstructure images generated from these simulations across the entire span of parameters, Θ allows for a wide range of microstructural features to be generated. The span of input parameters and resulting family of M -states builds the microstructure domain on which to

explore how changing the processing parameters impacts the resulting microstructural features. Figure 3.1 shows example microstructures at corresponding θ -parameter pairs across the processing domain, where each individual microstructure was generated with the same random seed, ξ , so that the deterministic information is the same and the spatial location of features is similar from one microstructure to the next, giving visual parity for easier interpretation of differences in microstructures across the domain.

Figure 3.1: Phase field material manifold from input conditions η and κ .

3.1.2 Manifold Sampling and Stochastic Approximation of M-State Information

In exploring the \mathcal{M} -manifold, a dataset of 25,000 microstructure images was generated by uniformly sampling the Θ -processing space as a Poisson point process for a set of 1000 M^θ -states. For each M^θ -state, 25 m -instances were generated by seeding the initial concentration c , from a Gaussian noise-field, ξ , having a mean value of η and numerically solving the Cahn-Hilliard equation for that set of (η, κ, ξ) initial conditions. Each of the 25 m -instances are independent and identically distributed (iid) random variables sampled from the same probability distribution as defined by their M -state.

The choice of 1000 M -states was made *a priori*, as this is a sufficient number of points needed for a reliable dimensionality estimation of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, as described later in Section 3.2.1. In order to balance dataset size and simulation time against the convergence of the microstructure descriptors for each M -state, 25 m -instances were generated for each M -state for a total of 25,000 simulations. This was justified *a posteriori* by the error bands on the estimate of the average persistence silhouettes.

Using Equation 2.4, each of the 1000 \hat{M}^θ approximations are calculated as the average microstructure descriptors, \bar{D}^θ . Individual descriptor vectors were calculated for each of the 25,000 m -instances, and approximations of the M -state descriptors were calculated by averaging each of the 25 m -instances in each of the 1000 M -states. Figure 3.2 shows the sampled states across the processing domain, with each point representing M -state a pair of processing parameters. Each point is colored according to its θ -parameters, with the amount of red corresponding to the η parameter and the amount of blue corresponding to the κ parameter. This color scheme is used throughout this work as a tool for visual parity in understanding the different data projections of the processing, structure, and material manifolds.

Figure 3.2: Processing parameter-material manifold with sampled M -states colored by red/blue parameter pair.

Revisiting the processing-structure feedback loop from Figure 2.1, while physically the forward process goes directly from the processing domain to the structure domain, the material state is not known until descriptors are calculated on m -instances from the generating process (phase-field), approximating the M -state descriptor from there. The inverse process, g , maps back from \hat{M} to $\hat{\Theta}$, or the recovered parameters. This revised diagram is shown in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Updated invertible mapping flowchart through stochastic approximation of M -state information.

3.1.3 Microstructure Descriptors

Using the dataset described in Section 3.1.2, three different reduced-order microstructure descriptors were calculated to compare the quality of descriptors in representing individual microstructures, as well as in constructing the material manifold itself. The descriptors chosen were persistent homology (PH), two-point correlation function (NPT), and average chord length (ACL). Descriptor calculations were done on each image, reducing the dimensionality of the m -instances from the ambient, image space, $m \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times 256}$, to that of the descriptor space: $D_{PH} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 100}$, $D_{NPT} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 100}$, and $D_{ACL} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ respectively.

Persistent Homology:

Persistent homology is a topological data analysis technique that is able to summarize the connectivity of microstructures over a range of length-scales [46]. Persistence silhouettes are one method in which persistent homology data can be summarized [47] and were chosen for this work because of the vector-based representation of persistent homology data. This allowed for simple integration with the computational and statistical analysis methods. Persistent homology calculations were done using the Geometry Understanding in Higher Dimensions (GUDHI) [48] and giotto-tda [49] python packages.

Persistence calculations were done on each image in ambient space $m \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times 256}$, reducing the dimensionality to that of the silhouette, $D_{PH} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 100}$. First, the persistence diagram for each image was calculated with giotto-tda’s ‘CubicalPersistence’ function. The diagram was calculated for a periodic cubical complex on both the x and y axes, given that the phase field simulations themselves were periodic. From there, the silhouettes were calculated using the ‘Silhouette’ function, with a power weighting of 1.0 (unweighted), and with a bin size of 100 - returning two 1×100 silhouette curves, one for each homology dimension. The

decision to use a bin size of 100 was chosen arbitrarily as the default value and does not need to match the number of bins in the original filtration series (e.g. 256 for the 0-255 grayscale filtration). From there, the M -state average silhouettes were calculated for the 0D and 1D curves, resulting in the final representation of $D_{PH} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 100}$. Figure 3.4 shows an example of a microstructure and its corresponding persistence silhouette, with one silhouette curve for the 0D topological features (components/black phase) and a second curve for the 1D topological features (holes/white phase).

Figure 3.4: Reference microstructure and corresponding persistence silhouette.

Two-Point Statistics:

N-point correlation statistics are a commonly used method for microstructure informatics [50]. The two-point correlation function describes the probability of finding vectors of random positions, directions, and magnitudes that have heads/tails in the same phase. This information is able to describe microstructural information like precipitate width and spacing, as well as capture averaged information like volume fraction.

Similarly to the persistence calculations, the 2-point correlation function was used to find a reduced-order microstructure descriptor, going from the ambient dimensionality of $m \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times 256}$ down to the radially-integrated autocorrelation vector, $D_{NPT} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 100}$. PoreSpy [51] was used to calculate the descriptor vectors using the ‘two_point_correlation’ function. The images were first binarized before calculating the autocorrelation vector with periodic boundaries on the x and y dimensions. The dataset used in this work contains purely-isotropic microstructures, meaning the vector form of the NPT function can be used as opposed to the full-field image. Figure 3.5 shows an example of a microstructure and its corresponding two-point autocorrelation function.

Figure 3.5: Reference microstructure and corresponding 2-point autocorrelation function.

Average Chord Length:

The average chord length was included as an alternative microstructure descriptor to test the manifold recovery qualities of a greatly-reduced order descriptor. Due to the nature of its calculation, the ACL is inherently a local-state descriptor and cannot capture the effects of long-range order in a microstructure. It was initially chosen as a simplification of the

chord length density (CLD) function and was expected to fail at manifold recovery due to the extreme reduction in dimensionality.

In contrast to NPT, CLD calculates the probability of a chord with length r contained wholly within a single phase [24]. While the full CLD function is useful for assessing connectivity properties like percolation, reducing that second-order representation from a distribution of measurements down to a first-order average with the ACL limits the description of microstructural features down to “how wide are precipitates on average” and “how much spacing is there between precipitates on average”.

Two different representations of the ACL descriptor were compared: the ACL of a single phase, arbitrarily chosen as the white phase, and the ACL of both phases. These two descriptors are notated as “ACL-1” and “ACL-2”. PoreSpy was used for the ACL calculations, calculating a reduced-order descriptor in $D_{ACL-1} \in \mathbb{R}^1$ and $D_{ACL-2} \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The ‘apply_chords’ function was used to calculate the length of white-phase vectors in one orthogonal direction. From there, the ‘count_chords’ function was used to count the length of chords applied in the previous function and averaged to return the average chord length. This process was repeated on the image inverse to determine the average chord length of the black phase. Again, because the dataset is isotropic, the descriptor was only calculated for a single orthogonal direction. Figure 3.6 shows an example of a microstructure and its corresponding average chord lengths for the black and white phases, with chords drawn over the reference sample shown in blue and red for the black and white phases respectively.

Figure 3.6: Reference microstructure and corresponding chord lengths for black phase (shown in blue) and white phase (shown in red).

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Dimensionality Estimation

The estimation of system dimensionality through a nearest-neighbor approach is used as one method for assessing the quality of the microstructure descriptors. In this work, dimensionality estimation was used as verification method to determine the quality of the chosen descriptors, but could alternatively be applied to estimate the dimensionality of an unknown system in an effort to determine the number of controlling parameters. Developed by [52] and applied for material manifold exploration by [32], the Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE)-based nearest-neighbor dimensionality estimation technique is a method for recovering the intrinsic dimensionality of a system. For the well-defined phase field system used in this work, it is known that its intrinsic dimensionality is two, as the entire process can be described by changing the two input θ -parameters, η and κ . The third parameter, ξ , has a major impact on the actual micrographs themselves, but does not This method relies

on having a distance metric between M -states in order to construct the nearest-neighbor network between microstructure classes.

For the chosen microstructure descriptors, a 1000×1000 matrix of pairwise MDD values between each of the M -state descriptors is calculated and used in the estimation of the intrinsic dimensionality of the manifold. Three different dimensionality assessments were completed: a comparison of 1000 little- m microstructures having the same initial seed, 1000 little- m microstructures having random initial seeds, and a comparison of the big- M representations of the full dataset. The two little- m comparisons were calculated to show the inability of the direct image distance to capture meaningful microstructure information when stochastic variation is introduced to the system. For the same seed dataset, little- m samples with similar θ -parameters have similar spatial, deterministic information. In this case, the direct image distance is able to construct a correct nearest-neighbor network, resulting in an accurate dimensionality estimation of 2.15, as shown in Table 3.1. This descriptor distance falls apart when the images are generated using a random seed, changing the initial state of the simulation and the resulting microstructures have no shared spatial information with results shown in Table 3.2. In this case, the dimensionality estimation returns 119.86, lower than the ambient dimensionality of \mathbb{R}^{65536} for 256×256 images, but an intractable representation for manifold construction and application.

When utilizing all 25 m -instances to calculate the \hat{M} -approximation, the results show that the three main descriptors (PH, NPT, and ACL-2) are able to successfully recover the true intrinsic dimensionality of the system, shown in Table 3.3, successfully capturing the stochasticity of the system and recovering a manifold having the minimum amount of parameters necessary. To visualize this, Section 3.2.4 plots 2D representations of the \hat{M} -approximation domain. The ACL-1 descriptor recovers a dimensionality of 1, that is to be expected as the ACL-1 descriptor itself is only a single value.

Table 3.1: Same Seed, Little m
MLE Dimensionality Estimation

Same Seed, Little m		
	μ	σ
Direct Image Distance	2.15	0.55
PH Distance	2.80	1.16
NPT Distance	2.07	0.65
ACL-2 Distance	1.92	0.67
ACL-1 Distance	1.00	0.31

Table 3.2: Random Seed, Little m
MLE Dimensionality Estimation

Random Seed, Little m		
	μ	σ
Direct Image Distance	119.86	41.00
PH Distance	2.74	1.00
NPT Distance	2.22	0.67
ACL-2 Distance	1.98	0.61
ACL-1 Distance	1.00	0.33

Table 3.3: Big M Nearest-Neighbor MLE Dimensionality Estimation

Random Seed, Big M		
	μ	σ
PH Distance	2.08	0.86
NPT Distance	1.83	0.57
ACL-2 Distance	1.94	0.60
ACL-1 Distance	1.00	0.32

3.2.2 Invertibility Assessment: Parameter Recovery using KNN Regression

In order to verify that the chosen descriptors are capturing and encoding information representative of the M -states, two regression models were trained to recover the input parameters to the phase field model used to generate the microstructures themselves. This is beginning to look at the *invertibility* requirement of an informative microstructure representation from Section 3.4.1, but in a manifold-averaged sense. Further assessment on the invertibility of different descriptor choices is needed to understand how invertibility shifts across the span of the manifold.

Support vector regression (SVR) and K-Neighbors Regression (KNN) are supervised regression models capable of predicting target values (θ -parameters for phase field model) from the predictor variables (microstructure D -descriptor vectors). For this analysis, the dataset of 1000 M -classes was separated into training/testing subsets using an 80/20 split. Scikit-Learn’s ‘LinearSVR’ and ‘KNeighborsRegressor’ models were used [53] with default model parameters. For the ‘LinearSVR’ model, D -descriptor vectors were passed directly as the predictor variables. For the ‘KNeighborsRegressor’ model, 1000×1000 pairwise MDD matrices for each of the descriptor methods were passed directly using the function’s ‘precomputed’ flag.

Tables 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, and 3.7 show regression model results in terms of the models’ coefficient of determination (R^2) and root mean squared error (RMSE) values. The R^2 value shows how well a model fits the dataset by reporting the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variable. The RMSE reports on average how far apart the predicted values were from the true values and can be directly interpreted in terms of $\Delta\theta$, or the average difference in recovered parameters.

Table 3.4: R^2 - LinearSVR

	Combined	Parameters	
		η	κ
PH	0.9512	0.9361	0.9663
NPT	0.9919	0.9992	0.9846
ACL-2	0.9786	0.9924	0.9647
ACL-1	0.3178	0.6237	0.0120

Table 3.5: RMSE - LinearSVR

	Combined	Parameters	
		η	κ
PH	0.0313	0.0351	0.0269
NPT	0.0132	0.0040	0.0182
ACL-2	0.0213	0.0121	0.0276
ACL-1	0.1195	0.0853	0.1458

When comparing the R^2 values of the two models, it can be seen that the PH, NPT, and ACL-2 descriptors all succeed in their abilities to recover the θ -parameters. The LinearSVR

Table 3.6: R^2 - KNR

	Combined	Parameters	
		η	κ
PH	0.9811	0.9893	0.9729
NPT	0.8729	0.9998	0.7459
ACL-2	0.9933	0.9990	0.9875
ACL-1	0.4385	0.8451	0.0318

Table 3.7: RMSE - KNR

	Combined	Parameters	
		η	κ
PH	0.0199	0.0144	0.0241
NPT	0.0523	0.0018	0.0740
ACL-2	0.0120	0.0044	0.0164
ACL-1	0.1092	0.0547	0.1444

results, shown in Table 3.4 show the NPT descriptor as the highest-performing model, with superb recovery of the η parameter, and very high recovery of the κ parameter. The η parameter’s R^2 value of 0.9992 is not unexpected for the NPT descriptor, as the volume fraction of the microstructure images are explicitly encoded in the descriptor vector. However, when comparing the NPT’s LinearSVR results to the KNR model, the NPT descriptor becomes the lowest-performing descriptor of the three (ACL-1 excluded). I believe this discrepancy in result is due to the nature of the NPT distance metrics in constructing a nearest-neighbor network to predict parameters. The KNR model has a similar R^2 for the η parameter, but drastically decreases for the κ parameter. I hypothesize that this is due to the relative sensitivity of the NPT descriptor to changes in η over changes in κ , where differences in η lead to distances orders of magnitude greater than differences in κ . Thus, when the KNR model is predicting parameters based off of the nearest neighbors with respect to MDD distance, it can much more readily distinguish between M -states with different η values.

The invertibility assessment was performed with a parameter recovery goal of $\text{RMSE} \leq 0.05$, as this is the $\Delta\theta$ at which humans can begin to differentiate between M -states. Aside from the NPT’s lack of sensitivity in the κ parameter for the KNR model, the three main descriptors (PH, NPT, ACL-2) all meet this minimum RMSE threshold.

Looking at the performance of the ACL-2 and ACL-1 descriptors, it was expected to see that the ACL-1 descriptor failed to recover the input parameters due to both the limited information available to the model in the ACL-1 descriptor, as well as the fundamentally ill-posed nature of attempting to recover data in \mathbb{R}^2 from \mathbb{R}^1 . That being said, the ACL-1's η R^2 for the KNR model was unexpectedly high. Along with the ACL-2's ability to recover the system dimensionality, it was quite surprising to see just how well it performed at the invertibility assessment, on average outperforming both the PH and NPT descriptors.

While there is certainly more that can be done to improve these regression model results in terms of model selection and hyperparameter tuning, the inclusion of two different models in this section is moreso to illustrate how changing the inverse model can drastically change the quality of recovered parameters for a given microstructure descriptor. When assessing the invertibility of different manifold construction techniques, performance is not just a function of descriptor choice, but also regression model choice. Some descriptors may excel for a linear regression model, while others may perform better using non-linear approaches.

Full-Cycle Invertibility Example

Cyclic invertibility is needed due to the highly iterative nature of materials development. If the inverse model is not able to accurately map between domain and co-domain, sequential iterations will begin to fall off of their target microstructures, leading to poor optimization in the exploration of the material design space. Figure 3.7 shows an example of what one full iterative loop looks like, beginning with input parameters ($\eta = 0.04, \kappa = 0.58$) and the micrograph generated from those parameters in 3.7(a). From there, the D_{PH} descriptor vector was calculated on that image and passed through the LinearSVR regression model to recover its predicted parameters: ($\eta = 0.02, \kappa = 0.57$). Those parameters were passed back into the phase field generator (with the same random seed) to generate the micrograph

shown in Figure 3.7(b). While there are some small changes in connectivity in the image, on the whole, the regenerated microstructure is extremely close to the input microstructure.

Figure 3.7: Example microstructure and its full-cycled comparison.

3.2.3 Stability: Effect of Stochastic Sampling

As a more qualitative analysis than the earlier sections, the stability assessment serves to understand the material manifold’s ability to separate the entropic effects of randomly sampled microstructures (variations in spatial information) from the distribution of instances around a M -state on the manifold [54]. Stability in this sense refers to stability in the Big M domain, where a small change in the processing domain corresponds to a small change in the M domain. Critically, navigation must be performed in the M domain. The little m representations themselves are too sensitive to changes in spatial information, and the corresponding neighborhood of samples in the m domain is not helpful with respect to navigability. Essentially, we want our material state descriptors to be agnostic to the aleatoric noise inherent in the stochastic nature of microstructure, enabling efforts to be focused on the relationship between processing and structure itself. This is achieved by estimating the latent domain representation of the \mathcal{M} -manifold from a finite number of m -instances.

This approach to microstructure analysis has roots in information theory and is useful both for a local understanding of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, such as in understanding the distribution of m -instances within one M -state [55], as well in the global, navigational sense. Representative volume elements (RVEs) and statistically equivalent representative volume elements (SERVEs) [56, 57] emerged as a method for characterizing microstructural information by establishing a minimum volume needed to capture a representative area of microstructural features - typically over a range defined by the characteristic length scale of desired features.

For our work, we are extracting information from the sample ensemble to estimate the distribution of microstructures within a M -state in the form of the sample average, following the ergodic hypothesis in which for the limit as samples tend to infinity, the sample mean approaches the distribution mean [58]. Ensemble-averaged microstructure statistics have been shown to be largely representative of distributions, allowing for a subset of m -instances to be used to perform property simulations on and achieve a result similar to that of the entire population [50]. This comes at the cost of losing out on distribution information, such as microstructures that exist at the tails of the distribution, or microstructures with relatively extreme instantiations of features that could lead to variations in material performance.

Figure 3.8 shows the effect of stochastic averaging on “smoothing” the manifold and its ability to establish meaningful neighbor relationships between M -states. This figure shows principal component analysis of D_{PH} calculated on individual m -instances and projected into \mathbb{R}^3 , a process further described in Section 3.2.4. Figure 3.8a is a plot of the D_{PH} of all 25,000 m -instances projected into the reduced domain. Figure 3.8b is a plot of the projections of one m -instance from each M -state, for a total of 1000 points. Figure 3.8c is a plot of the \hat{M} -approximations for all M -states as the ensemble average of m -instances. These figures serve to illustrate the stochastic representation of microstructure’s ability to establish a navigable co-domain by which the processing-structure relationships can be performed.

The PCA projection was trained using the \hat{M} -approximations as shown in Figure 3.8c, and subsequently applied to the datasets in a and b, allowing us to see where the individual $D_{PH}(m)$ descriptors lie in relation to the underlying manifold. As such, the figures will be discussed in reference to Figure 3.8c. Figure 3.8a shows a “thick” manifold - a fundamentally an oxymoronic term, as a manifold must be infinitely thin by definition, but nevertheless - where the thickness is due to the stochastic distribution of m -instances around their underlying M -states. Figure 3.8b shows a “noisy” manifold, with sharp peaks between neighboring instances.

Figure 3.8: PCA projections of D_{PH} descriptors for (a) all 25,000 m -instances, (b) one m -instance for each M -state, and (c) \hat{M} -approximations for all M -states.

3.2.4 Manifold Visualization

Lower-dimensional projections ($\mathbb{R}^2/\mathbb{R}^3$) of the higher-dimensional microstructure descriptor spaces were used to qualitatively explore the approximation of the material manifold. A general assessment of the coherency and navigability of the manifolds can be done by looking for continuity between the parameter-based projection of the manifold and those constructed based on the microstructure descriptors.

For each of the manifold projection techniques, the family of \hat{M} -approximations for all θ -parameter sets in the material system were used to find low-dimensional projections of the manifold.

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a linear dimensionality reduction (DR) technique that transforms higher-dimensional data into a lower dimension, calculating the linear combination of variables in the original representation that explain the greatest variance in the system [59]. It has previously been used for exploring material systems [60] and is a quick method for exploring linear relationships in the embedded microstructure domain.

t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (TSNE) was chosen as a manifold projection technique as it constructs a non-linear manifold based on the local similarities/relationships between data points [61]. This was appealing for our method, as it utilizes the MDD between \hat{M}^θ -approximations to construct the nearest-neighbor relationships, and the degree of locality vs globality of the projection can be tuned using the 'perplexity' parameter.

These manifold projection techniques were calculated using the Scikit-Learn's 'PCA' and 'TSNE' functions. The data was taken from the embedded microstructure domain, $\hat{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{100}$, down to a lower projected domain in \mathbb{R}^2 . The dimensionality of the projected domain was chosen in conjunction with the results from the dimensionality estimation in Section 3.2.1, as the minimum dimensionality of the projected domain for an interpretable visualization should match the estimated dimensionality, $\mathbb{R}^{estimated}$, or $\mathbb{R}^{estimated+1}$ in the case of a surface embedded in a higher dimensional domain.

Figure 3.9 shows manifold projections of the \hat{M} -approximations using D_{NPT} for the (b) PCA and (c) TSNE techniques respectively. These plots use the same red/blue color scheme established in Section 3.1.2 to qualitatively interpret how cohesive these manifold approximations are by looking for smooth color gradients across the surfaces in comparison to Figure 3.9(a). The PCA projection shown in Figure 3.9(b) is visually similar to that of

the Θ domain in (a), looking like a 2D plane with a slight bend to it. It is important to note the change in scale from Component 1 to Component 2 in Figure 3.9(b), where Component 1 is two orders of magnitude greater than that of Component 2. In contrast, the TSNE projection shown in 3.9(c) looks more like a thin ribbon or 1D line embedded in 2D space, unable to separate out the κ parameter, condensing the blue/black and red/pink regions of processing space. This result, paired with the analysis from Section 3.2.2 and the magnitude difference in the PCA projection gives rise to my hypothesis that the MDD values are skewed against the κ parameter.

Figure 3.9: (b) PCA and (c) TSNE projections of \hat{M} -approximations of the \mathcal{M} -manifold using D_{NPT}

Figure 3.10 shows the PCA and TSNE manifold projections of the \hat{M} -approximations using D_{PH} . In contrast to D_{NPT} , the PCA projection shows more artifacts of the descriptor choice and the TSNE projection gives a more cohesive manifold projection overall. Again looking like a ‘bent’ version of the processing domain in Figure 3.10(a), the PCA projection in Figure 3.10(b) shows an increase in sparsity in the intermediate regime of the manifold, having densely-packed points of M -states along the two extreme edges (in terms of η). This artifact comes about due to the increased rate of change of D_{PH} with respect to $\Delta\theta$ in the intermediate, highly-connected regime of the parameter space (η between approx. -0.05 and 0.05). This region on the \mathcal{M} -manifold is seen as “unstable” with respect to the MDD calculations on the D_{PH} as the persistent homology descriptor is sensitive to changes in system topology and connectivity as the M -states undergo a phase inversion and the matrix and precipitating phases swap. The TSNE projection has much more evenly distributed M -states in the structure domain, while having a few interesting characteristics described ahead in Section 3.3.1. As TSNE has the perplexity parameter to tune the local/global nature of the projection, it is able to compress and decompress the various non-linear regions of the domain.

Figure 3.11 plots the M -states in the embedded D_{ACL-2} domain, without the need for dimensionality reduction via PCA or TSNE, as the descriptor calculation latent domain down to 2 dimensions. Figure 3.11(b) shows this embedding with the x-axis corresponding to the average chord length of the white phase, and the y-axis corresponding to the average chord length of the black phase. Following the prior dimensionality and invertibility assessments, this projection of the data validates those results, establishing a cohesive latent representation of the M -states and allowing for navigation. While it remains to be seen if this simple

Figure 3.10: (b) PCA and (c) TSNE projections of \hat{M} -approximations of the \mathcal{M} -manifold using D_{PH}

descriptor in \mathbb{R}^2 can be used for forward analysis, for example in material property prediction, it provides one great benefit in terms of navigability and interpretability in that each of the latent domains relates directly to a physical microstructural feature.

Figure 3.11: (b) 2D embedding of \hat{M} -approximation of the \mathcal{M} -manifold using D_{ACL-2}

3.3 Discussion

3.3.1 Mapping Microstructure: From Processing to Structure Domains

Building from the results in the Sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2 and visualizations in Section 3.2.4, different approaches to summarizing salient microstructural information, as well as interpreting that information through inverse models or dimensionality reduction techniques provide alternative interpretations of the underlying domain, although no one approach is inherently incorrect or better than the others. Revisiting Figure 3.10(c) with a slightly adjusted perplexity parameter for easier visualization, Figure 3.12 shows a TSNE projection of the D_{PH} representation of the latent domain. This visualization technique highlights the natural separation of the \mathcal{M} -states into three different regions along the structure manifold: (1) the primary black region on the left, (2) the intermediate region in the middle, and (3) the primary white region on the right. With this non-linear representation of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, it becomes immediately apparent how to navigate the manifold in such a way to either retain a

microstructure having a certain topology, or to traverse the manifold and enter a new regime of connectivity. On the other hand, D_{NPT} and D_{ACL-2} provide much more consistent, linear representations of the data, with more even steps from one M -state to the other, excelling at extracting a linear representation of the underlying \mathcal{M} -manifold.

Figure 3.12: 2D unraveling of TNSE projection of D_{PH} .

3.4 Manifold Mapping through Charts and Atlases

Of additional benefit in defining the material state space on a manifold is the mathematical notion of atlases and charts. An atlas describes a topological manifold (our \mathcal{M} -manifold, for example) as a set of charts mapping from a subset on \mathcal{M} to Euclidean space [62]. This concept fits exceptionally well with our notion of the material state space and \mathcal{M} -manifold,

with each of the avenues with which we can learn about the underlying manifold making up an individual chart, and the summation of those charts constructing an atlas. Figure 3.13 shows an example of how different charts may represent the \mathcal{M} -manifold in linear and non-linear domains, based off of the processing and structure projections of data.

Figure 3.13: Atlas set of descriptor charts.

Each of the microstructure descriptor choices and subsequent dimensionality reduction techniques can be used to formulate a chart, that can be used to attempt to elucidate more information on the unknown, underlying \mathcal{M} -manifold [63]. As more information is added to the atlas, our understanding of the \mathcal{M} -manifold becomes increasingly clear, as does our ability to navigate along it. For the materials domain chosen in this work, charts extracted

through QRM are *compatible* with each other, meaning they map to the same region on the \mathcal{M} -manifold. This allows us to establish bi-directional mappings between domains, mapping from one domain to the next and implicitly passing through the \mathcal{M} -manifold. Ultimately, these charts allow us to establish a mathematical basis on which to learn the complex, high-dimensional relationships between processing and structure.

Charts and atlases also extend to material systems with information beyond our current knowledge, such as in inaccessible regions of material state space. For example, potential new materials that could be developed that we do not currently have the manufacturing capabilities to create. These systems tie back in to the notion of the “New World” of materials and manufacturing. Methods like additive manufacturing are able to create highly-controlled microstructures and materials states that were previously inaccessible with traditional manufacturing techniques. Additionally, the material manifold may have blind spots. The full span of the processing domain may not reach all the regions of the material state manifold.

3.4.1 Attributes of an “Informative” Microstructure Representation

In search of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, we have determined necessary criteria for microstructure descriptors to be conducive to the construction of a continuous space. The attributes required are outlined below and shown in Figure 3.14:

Hierarchical: Microstructure is inherently a multi-scale problem. Fullwood et al. as the “myriad features of internal structure of heterogeneous materials across length scales ranging from the atomic through the mesoscale to approaching the macroscale” [4]. Being able to quantify features spanning across multiple length scales and understand the effects of both short- and long-range order are key to having a robust understanding of microstructure.

Metrizable: Having a sense of closeness is crucial for defining the neighborhood relationships between M -states. Strictly, metrizable requires the Big M domain (\mathcal{M} -Manifold) to

Figure 3.14: Attributes of an “informative” microstructure representation.

exist on a metric space with the ability to calculate true distance measures between M -states. This property of the \mathcal{M} -Manifold is utilized for many of the domain analysis techniques.

Invertible: Invertibility is the ability of a model to recover the original input parameters from the descriptor space. This is a characteristic of the inverse process: i.e. the mapping from microstructure space back to processing space $g : M \rightarrow \Theta$.

Resolvable: Resolvability is the notion of having distinguishable descriptors, or being able to recognize different M -states within some given parameter-threshold. This is inherently a characteristic of the forward process, meaning that it is defined by the mapping from processing space to microstructure space $f : \Theta \rightarrow M$ (or more correctly, to microstructure descriptor space).

3.4.2 Greater Applications to Materials Development

While much of the work presented in this chapter has been in establishing the mathematical framework to construct an approximation of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, this methodology can then be applied for materials discovery and development problems. At its core, this framework is extremely flexible and able to be adapted to the needs and restrictions of a given problem. Microstructure descriptors, or even more generically, material state descriptors can be chosen to focus on material features and information that is important for each application. One major benefit of this quantitative approach is that it avoids the need for the training of machine learning models in the mapping from processing to structure domain. In doing so, this approach has lower requirements for dataset sizes (although more data will improve the manifold’s ability to capture stochastic noise), as well as retains a degree of physical meaning to the latent space.

Figure 3.15 shows an example of manifold construction (everything done up to this point), followed by manifold implementation and the possibilities of how to apply this learned domain knowledge. After construction, first steps should be to assess the quality of the constructed manifold in terms of resolvability and invertibility, shown in Chapter 5. Domain knowledge can also be integrated with machine learning techniques to improve model understanding and capabilities, shown in Chapter 4. Beyond this, the \mathcal{M} -manifold has potential in performing exploration/exploitation analysis in novel materials domains, integrating with

Bayesian optimization methods like active learning to intelligently sample across new design spaces. Moving forward to property connections, \mathcal{M} -manifold assessment can be used to guide materials development to reach a final desired state.

Figure 3.15: Manifold workflow and further applications.

3.5 Conclusions

Using a data-driven implementation of the stochastic representation of microstructure, we were able to extract a series of low-dimensional representations of the underlying \mathcal{M} -manifold that work together to establish material domain knowledge and understand the complex relationships between processing conditions and resultant material structure.

Chapter 4: Neural Network-Based Domain Exploration

4.1 Introduction

As a parallel approach to the quantitative stochastic representation of microstructure, machine learning and deep neural networks have great potential in understanding the complex relationships between processing, structure, and properties due to their abilities to abstract information in high dimensions, beyond the levels of human-interpretability.

A secondary focus of this work was to develop a general-purpose machine learning representation of microstructure with the goal of establishing a single computational model that can be used for both material property prediction as well as for the synthesis of new microstructure data. While this goal was not ultimately achieved, lessons learned throughout the developmental process highlight the need for navigable representations of the latent material domain. Integration of ML models with the material manifold framework allow for increased interpretability, improving application of trained networks and increasing user confidence in the “black box” nature of DL.

4.1.1 Deep Learning

With roots in computer vision, deep learning (DL) has become a dominant force in the field of image analysis, with its ability to extract information and relationships between data in high, non-linear dimensions. This is primarily due to DL model architectures, in which

data is passed through multiple processing layers to learn abstract representations of data, with convolutional neural networks (CNNs) representing an extremely popular approach for DL on image data [64].

Autoencoders (AE) are an expansion on the traditional CNN architecture that feature paired encoder-decoder layers, similar in concept to image compression in which a full-field image is encoded from the ambient domain down to a compressed representation, or latent space, and then decompressed back to the dimensions of the original image. This style of encoder-decoder architecture works together to create the most informative “latent space” representation of data possible, as the encoder works to extract features from an image and compress that information and the decoder can be used to validate that the latent representation is enough information to recover the initial image [65].

Variational autoencoders (VAEs) take this architecture one step further and incorporate Bayesian inference into the latent representation of data [66]. In this approach, the network is designed to learn distributions rather than point estimates of data, leading to a continuous latent space that can be effectively sampled for generation tasks. The output of the encoder is the parameter of a probability distribution function.

VAEs have become popular as tools for data generation in both computer and materials science, as they capture information on the underlying distributions of features within a dataset [67]. By sampling from those latent distributions and decoding, new realizations of data can be generated. A neural network’s latent space can be thought of as a direct analogue to our material manifold, wherein each point in the latent space represents a material state, or the features necessary to describe that material state.

4.2 Adversarial Hierarchical Variational Autoencoder

In pursuit of adapting techniques developed for traditional computer vision to applications in materials science, several architecture augmentations on existing VAE networks were applied. Two key materials concepts were focused on: the hierarchical nature of material microstructures, and the close relationships between neighboring material states. Because of this desire, concepts from two different network architectures were combined. The Nouveau Variational Autoencoder (NVAE) architecture developed by NVIDIA [68] contains a multitude of latent spaces at each convolutional layer. These multiple latent spaces allow for the capture of both long- and short-range order features at the different encoding depths. Adversarial autoencoder (AAE) networks [69] integrate adversarial training with VAEs by training an adversarial discriminator network on the latent space representations of data, enforcing desired characteristics on the training of latent distributions learned by the encoder. Typically, adversarial networks are trained against an image generator and work to improve the quality of synthetic images. However, the AAE approach is more focused on establishing a dense, coherent latent space understanding of the system for improved dimensionality reduction and visualization. These motivations integrate well with our desire for extracting the material manifold. The NVAE architecture was integrated with the AAE’s latent space adversarial training to form the Adversarial Hierarchical Variational Autoencoder (AHVAE).

The work in this section represents the collaborative efforts of Octavian Donca, Dr. Mengfei Yuan, and Dr. Ashley Lenau, with Octavian acting as the primary developer of the AHVAE architecture and Dr. Yuan adapting the trained network to establish additional decoder networks.

4.2.1 Architecture and Training

The AHVAE architecture, shown in Figure 4.1 was built off of a traditional U-Net architecture [70], with a series of 4 blocks of layers consisting of 3×3 convolutional layers, ReLU activation, and a 2×2 max pooling layer to downsample the image. Images were input into the network at a dimensionality of $(128, 128, 1)$, at which point depth was increased to $(128, 128, 32)$, before block downsampling embedded images down to $(64, 64, 64)$, $(32, 32, 128)$, $(16, 16, 256)$, and ending with a latent representation of $(8, 8, 512)$. The NVAE’s original motivation for increasing network depth at the outset of training from 1 to 32 was to improve the network’s ability to establish abstract connections, but it does come at the cost of increasing network complexity, which can become an issue both in terms of memory requirements during training, as well as in latent space analysis.

After encoding, the decoder network follows the inverse of the encoding blocks, upsampling from the latent dimensionality back to the ambient dimensionality. At this stage, skip connections are passed from the encoding stage across to the decoder to allow the AHVAE network to recover direct spatial information in an attempt to allow the latent space to extract characteristic microstructure information, but not explicit features (i.e. compress to “Big M” space, not “Little m” space). Additionally, the AHVAE network resamples from each of the intermediate latent spaces at each stage.

Five different loss functions were used to optimize the mapping between ambient and latent domains, with traditional reconstruction loss being used to assess the quality of reconstructed microstructures against their initial states. The mean squared error was used as the L_{recon} function, shown in Equation 4.1. Two different Kullback Leibler (KL) divergence loss functions were used for the VAE portion of the network, with $\mu_i(x)$ and $\sigma_i(x)$ as the estimated mean and variance solved by the encoder. To improve stability, the loss function solves for $\ln(\sigma^2(x))$ rather than $\sigma^2(x)$ directly, as shown in equation 4.3.

Figure 4.1: AHVAE network architecture.

$$L_{recon} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (x_i - x'_i)^2 \quad (4.1)$$

$$L_{KL} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_i^2(x) + \sigma_i^2(x) + \ln \sigma_i^2(x) - 1) \quad (4.2)$$

$$L_{KL} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mu_i^2(x) + \exp[\ln \sigma_i^2(x)] + [\ln \sigma_i^2(x)] - 1) \quad (4.3)$$

In addition to this traditional autoencoder/U-Net approach, the adversarial component of the network was utilized to improve the quality of the final compressed latent space, with the encoder part of the network acting as a generator, and a discriminator being used to better differentiate between samples generated from the prior distribution and the realistic samples. In Equation 4.4 and 4.5, L stands for number of layers in latent space, N stands for number of the samples in a batch, and z_i and z_j are the prior and the posterior distribution.

$$L_{gen} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N [\log(1 - d_x(z_{l,j}))] \right] \quad (4.4)$$

$$L_{disc} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \left[-\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [\log d_x(z_{l,i})] - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=N+1}^{2N} [\log(1 - d_x(z_{l,j}))] \right] \quad (4.5)$$

The AHVAE network was trained using the dataset of spinodal decomposition microstructures to encode and decode the images down to the latent domain. Table 4.1 shows examples of reconstructions using AE, VAE, and AHVAE networks. Quantitatively, the AHVAE network achieves the best visual fidelity in the reconstructed image, reducing the amount of blurring at the boundaries as commonly seen with VAE networks. Quantitatively, the AHVAE network also had the lowest L_1 norm of the three networks.

4.2.2 Latent Space Information Extraction

Given the fully-trained encoder from 4.2.1, additional purpose-built decoders were trained to extract and predict additional information from the information-rich latent space. These tests were completed to explore the hypothesis that autoencoder networks are able to compress material domains into a dense, informative latent space by which additional information can be extracted. Three additional decoder networks, shown in Figure 4.2 were developed and applied to the already-trained latent space to recover information implicitly present in

Table 4.1: Microstructure Reconstructions for AE, VAE, and AHVAE Networks

	Microstructure Reconstruction Example	L1 Norm
AE		0.034
VAE		0.079
AHVAE		0.009

the original images (processing parameters and microstructure descriptor), as well as predict new property information (stress response).

Material and Topological Information Extraction:

For the information extraction tests, the AHVAE encoder was used as a feature extractor, using shallow, fully-dense decoder layers trained to extract physical parameters from the encoded latent space. While information on these physical parameters were implicitly contained in the individual micrographs themselves, this information was never explicitly provided during the encoding stage. Two separate decoders were trained. One to recover the input parameters used to initialize the phase field simulation of the microstructures: the volume fraction and interfacial energy parameters. The second decoder was trained to recover the Betti numbers of the micrographs, a topological descriptor that counts the number

Figure 4.2: Additional decoders trained to extract and predict information from the AHVAE latent space.

of topological features (connected components and holes) in each image. Figure 4.3 shows the extraction of these features from the pre-trained latent space.

Material Property Prediction:

To further explore the capabilities of the AHVAE network an additional network was trained to predict the stress response of individual microstructure images to a given strain field. In this study, we trained an additional decoder to decompress the latent space back to the dimensionality of the original image domain and predict the von Mises stress field. An elasto-viscoplastic fast Fourier transform (EVP-FFT) based crystal plasticity solver was

Figure 4.3: Information recovery results of AHVAE models for the prediction of material and topological parameters.

used to simulate the stress response of the spinodal microstructures when they contained a stiff and a compliant phase. Simulated results were then used to train a separate decoder to decompress from the latent space back to the same dimensionality as the images, but instead recover the von Mises stress response, shown in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: von Mises stress response property prediction results of AHVAE model.

4.2.3 Architecture Drawbacks

Ultimately, the AHVAE network failed at being an all-in-one materials science network, lacking the ability to synthesize novel micrographs sampled from known populations. It is the author’s opinion that this failure is due chiefly to the rapid over-training of the network, likely due in part to the U-Net skip connections, leading to its failure in ability to understand groups of M -state microstructure as a generating process. The over-training led to a sparse, discontinuous latent space that could not be effectively sampled to synthesize new, similar microstructures. Sampling from the trained latent distributions only served to adjust the intensities of individual pixels, as shown in Figure 4.5, but if latent coordinates strayed too far from the original encoded positions, images quickly devolved into meaningless noise. Because of the skip connections and extremely high dimensions, the trained latent space was overly sparse, failing to establish relationships between m -instances of the same M -state. This inability to draw out M -state information limited the AHVAE networks capabilities in synthetic microstructure generation. The AHVAE excelled at information extraction from *individual* microstructure instances, although this may be due in part to the extreme depth allocated to each microstructure image, with the possibility that images were never truly “compressed” below their initial dimensionality and instead existed in convoluted representations of their full initial state. Despite this, the separately trained information extraction networks were able to extract information not explicitly encoded in the initial representation as well as predict full-field property responses.

Figure 4.5: Initial microstructure, x , and an AHVAE latent space sampled microstructure, x' , showing the AHVAE network's inability to change spatial microstructure features.

4.3 Denoising Diffusion Autoencoder

The challenge of developing a neural network architecture capable of extracting a latent space representation of the material manifold was revisited with the development of denoising diffusion autoencoders (DDAE) for image generation [71].

This section represents the excellent work of Maxwell Brown in adapting DDAE networks from the literature to the field of materials science, working in collaboration with Drs. Megna Shah and Jeff Simmons.

4.3.1 Architecture

The DDAE network was trained using the denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) architecture developed by Ho et al. [72] and sampled using the denoising diffusion implicit model (DDIM) architecture developed by Song et al. [73]. DDIMs are more efficient for sampling new microstructure images, with the added benefit of being deterministic, allowing for manifold navigation with visual parity between microstructure images as described

in Section 4.3.3. A key concept in the development of DDAEs is the establishment of two separate latent spaces: the semantic and stochastic latent spaces. In this construction, the semantic latent space is used to represent a state descriptor on an image. The stochastic latent space is used to generate new instances of images given a defined semantic encoding. This construction closely resembles our definition of M/m representations of materials, as well as the phase field simulation of our microstructure system in which we define a semantic representation of images (material processing parameters) and initialize a noise field to generate new m -instances.

Figure 4.6: DDAE network architecture.

For our network, input images were conditioned explicitly on the $\theta = (\eta, \kappa)$ parameter pairs used to generate the images from the phase field model. From there, the semantic

encoder maps the input conditions from \mathbb{R}^2 to \mathbb{R}^{32} , giving the network the freedom to establish its own higher-order relationships. Figure 4.7 shows a PCA projection of the trained semantic latent space for a series of 1000 θ parameter pairs, as compared to their positions in the initial parameter domain. Similarly to the projections shown in Chapter 3, the DDAE network is able to extract a dense, coherent latent space, maintaining neighbor relationships and the smooth color gradient from the original parameter domain. This is an important development over the AHVAE network, as the separation of semantic and stochastic variations allows the DDAE network to learn a “Big M” understanding of the data - or what it means for an image to belong to a specific M -state.

Figure 4.7: Sampled θ -parameters in the parameter domain and corresponding PCA projection of the trained DDAE semantic latent space.

4.3.2 Microstructure Generation

Implemented as a microstructure generation tool, the dual-latent space nature of the DDAE gives the user a great amount of control in the overall characteristics of the final desired microstructure with respect to the semantic and stochastic nature of the images.

In order to synthesize a new microstructure, points must be queried in both latent spaces, with the semantic coordinates defining the M -state to be synthesized, and the stochastic coordinates initializing the random noise field to be denoised into the final state, determining the m -instance, as shown in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: DDAE implemented as a microstructure generator.

By fixing your query coordinates in one of the two latent spaces at a time, two different things can be achieved:

- M -state generator: fixing a point in semantic latent space.
- Parallel m -instance generator: fixing a point in stochastic latent space

For fixing a point in the semantic latent space, repeated sampling of new positions in the stochastic latent space produces a set of “essentially equivalent” micrographs from a single M -state. Results for this style of decoding are shown in Figure 4.9a. Along with this network explicitly conditioned on the phase field input parameters, we trained a separate network

conditioned on the \hat{M} -approximations for each material state using the D_{NPT} descriptor. This idea enables two things: semantic conditioning and network training on microstructures with unknown input parameters based off of a quantitative descriptor of their semantic state, as well as the ability to generate microstructures at a desired position along the pre-defined \mathcal{M} -manifold. Results for the manifold-conditioned microstructures are shown in Figure 4.9. While these generated microstructures are visually-convincing to humans, more time is spent in assessing their qualities as far as matching the underlying populations of M -states in Chapter 5. Additionally, there are some issues in image “exposure”, wherein the mean pixel intensities do not quite match the input images. This is addressed as well in Chapter 5.

Figure 4.9: Example microstructure ensembles generated using the DDAE network trained with (a) parameter-conditioned semantic encoding and (b) a manifold-conditioned semantic encoding.

4.3.3 Latent Space Navigation

The second approach to applying the DDAE network as a microstructure generator is by fixing a point in the stochastic latent space and sampling of new positions in the semantic latent space. This produces a set of “parallel” micrographs, or realizations of what your original micrograph would look like if it were generated with a different set of processing

parameters. As the implemented DDAE decoding process is deterministic, the final, spatial positions of features will be similar for m -instances having similar processing conditions. Figure 4.10 shows an example of using the DDAE network to generate two different trajectories through the \mathcal{M} -manifold. For each trajectory, the stochastic information is fixed and the semantic information is incrementally adjusted to show a trajectory through the \mathcal{M} -manifold either increasing precipitate spacing or changing the dominant phase. It should be noted that these trajectories represent non-physical evolutions in microstructure states, navigating in the M domain itself from one state to the next, not along a trajectory of a single M -state evolving from initial to final spinodal decomposition.

Figure 4.10: DDAE microstructure generation showing latent space/ \mathcal{M} -manifold navigation over two different trajectories.

4.3.4 Discussion

The separation of system information into the two distinct latent spaces provided a key leap forward in improving the interpretability of deep learning models, a much needed benefit in improving our understanding of these machine learning models. The ability to query points in both the semantic and stochastic latent spaces greatly improves this network’s abilities

to be used as a tool for microstructure generation, as well as crucially enabled the DDAE to learn a dense, meaningful latent representation of the materials domain - a direct analogue to our \mathcal{M} -manifold.

4.4 Conclusions

Deep learning and neural networks are an excellent tool for materials development, able to extract meaningful relationships between process, structure, and properties in abstract, high-dimensional spaces. Careful attention to network architecture design is needed to allow networks to recognize clusters of semantically-similar microstructures (same M -state), a crucial step in reducing the dimensionality needed for accurate model performance and avoiding intractable representations of data.

Chapter 5: Statistical Tools for Manifold Assessment

5.1 Introduction

After the establishment of stochastic material state descriptors and manifolds, further statistical analysis can be performed to understand the properties of material systems, applied microstructure descriptors, and the chosen inverse models. This work is done in service of understanding the *resolvability* attribute of “informative” microstructure descriptors as established in Section 3.4.1 [74].

The work in this section was completed in collaboration with Alan Gan and Dr. Oksana Chkrebtii from OSU’s Department of Statistics. Their expertise and direction was fundamental in the application of statistical techniques and integration with the material manifold.

5.2 Resolvability

Resolvability, or the notion of having distinguishable descriptors, is closely tied to the idea of statistical sensitivity [75]. At its core, *resolvability* attempts to establish at what change in parameter, $\Delta\theta$, two different M -states can be distinguished. This property is inherently a function of the forward process, $f : \Theta \rightarrow M$, and in our case is dependent both on the generating process (phase field model/manufacturing process), as well as the

microstructure descriptor chosen to represent m -instances/ M -states. *Resolvability* is important in understanding manifold properties, such as determining unstable regions in processing space in which a small $\Delta\theta$ leads to a large change in the resulting microstructure, as well as in establishing uncertainty bounds, either in the process itself or in the subsequent state measurement.

5.2.1 Homogeneity Testing using the Metric Distribution Function

The work in this section was adopted directly from Wang et al.’s work in establishing the metric distribution function (MDF) as an approach for investigating probability measures in non-Euclidean domains by embedding data into a metric space for non-parametric statistical inference [76]. The following definitions and equations are taken from Section 4, “METRIC DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION BASED STATISTICAL METHODS”, of that work. Chiefly, this approach allows many already-developed statistical tests to be updated and applied to the complex domains where a metric distance function can be established. We have utilized this approach to assess the resolvability of our different microstructure descriptors utilizing the calculated MDDs.

The two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test is a non-parametric statistical test on the equality of probability distributions and can be used to test whether two samples come from the same distribution or not [77]. The KS test statistic is the supremum between two empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDFs), returning a value between $[0, 1]$ representing the distance between distributions. For a test statistic of 0, there is no distance between distributions. The metric Kolmogorov-Smirnov (MKS) test is an extension upon the traditional KS test, allowing us to calculate the distance between distributions on a metric domain using the pairwise distances between all samples within both groups. A statistical

hypothesis test can then be performed to determine the homogeneity of two groups - i.e. to test if two groups come from the same distribution.

For two unknown groups on a metric space, μ_1 and μ_2 , we want to know if they come from the same distribution, where $H_0 : \mu_1 = \mu_2$ and $H_a : \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$. Using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov divergence, the MKS test statistic can be estimated for two sets, \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} , where $\mathbf{X}_1 \dots \mathbf{X}_{n_1} \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mu_1$ and $\mathbf{Y}_1 \dots \mathbf{Y}_{n_2} \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mu_2$. The $MKS(\mu_1 || \mu_2)$ and $MKS(\mu_2 || \mu_1)$ divergences can be estimated using the empirical metric distribution functions (EMDFs) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{MKS}(\mu_1 || \mu_2) &= \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \max_{v \in \mathcal{X} \cup \mathcal{Y}} |F_{\mu_1, n_1}^M(\mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{v}) - F_{\mu_2, n_2}^B(\mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{v})|, \\ \widehat{MKS}(\mu_2 || \mu_1) &= \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \max_{v \in \mathcal{X} \cup \mathcal{Y}} |F_{\mu_1, n_1}^M(\mathbf{Y}_j, \mathbf{v}) - F_{\mu_2, n_2}^B(\mathbf{Y}_j, \mathbf{v})| \end{aligned} \quad (5.1)$$

and thus the MKS test statistic, $\widehat{MKS}(\mu_1, \mu_2)$, can be calculated by symmetrizing the MKS divergence,

$$\widehat{MKS}(\mu_1, \mu_2) = \widehat{MKS}(\mu_1 || \mu_2) + \widehat{MKS}(\mu_2 || \mu_1) \quad (5.2)$$

Conceptually, the MKS test works by picking two samples, calculating the distance between them, establishing an ‘exclusion radius’ around the first sample based off of that distance value, and counts the ratio of samples inside vs outside the exclusion radius, shown in Figure 5.1. This is performed for all pairs of samples in the same group and opposing groups and repeated exhaustively for all samples in both populations. Ultimately, the MKS test statistic, \widehat{MKS} , returns a value $[0, 2]$ describing the distance between distributions. After calculating the \widehat{MKS} , a permutation test can be performed to approximate the p -value. Permutation tests operate using *proof by contradiction* by rearranging the labels of samples between the two groups, shown in Figure 5.1b and recalculating the \widehat{MKS} test statistic many times to build a null distribution of test statistics. Then, the p -value is determined as

the proportion of null test statistics $\leq \widehat{MKS}$ test statistic for the original groups, μ_1 and μ_2 . For a p-value below a set α threshold ($\alpha=0.05$ in this work), the H_0 is rejected and the two groups do not come from the same distribution. For a p-value greater than the α threshold, we fail to reject the H_0 and are not able to determine that μ_1 and μ_2 do not come from the same distribution.

Figure 5.1: (a) Two groups of samples with initial labels and (b) permuted labels, and examples of exclusion radii for (c) in-group comparison and (d) out-of-group comparison.

Figure 5.2 shows an example of the MKS test performed using D_{NPT} on two neighboring M -states: $M^{667} : (\eta = 0.011, \kappa = 0.491)$ and $M^{834} : (\eta = 0.006, \kappa = 0.496)$. These two M -states have extremely similar θ -parameters and are visually quite similar, as seen in Figures 5.2c and 5.2c. D_{NPT} descriptor vectors were calculated for each of the 25 m -instances in both M -states, with an MDS projection of the resulting M -state distributions shown in Figure 5.2a. Despite having a small change in parameters, $\Delta\theta = 0.007$, the M -state distributions are visually separable using the D_{NPT} descriptor. Figure 5.2b shows the \bar{D}_{NPT} descriptors (\hat{M} -approximations) for these two M -states, where it can be seen that the two descriptors are slightly offset from one another. By performing an MKS test on these two M -states with 250 permutations, the \widehat{MKS} test statistic is estimated to be 1.62 with a corresponding p -value of 0.00. As $p < \alpha$, we reject H_0 and determine that the samples from M^{667} and M^{834} come from different distributions. The power of the MKS test comes in its ability to compare populations as a whole, rather than individual samples, but it is ultimately limited by the sensitivity of the chosen descriptor.

5.2.2 Local Manifold Resolvability Assessment

When expanding to local and regional subsets of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, the MKS test can be used to establish *resolvability* limits of different material state descriptors. MKS tests were performed for each of the three descriptors, D_{NPT} , D_{PH} , and D_{ACL-2} , comparing the reference M -state, $M^{667} : (\eta = 0.011, \kappa = 0.491)$, to its 40 nearest neighboring M -states (neighboring in terms of θ -parameters). Figures 5.3 and 5.4 show the resulting MDS distributions, \widehat{MKS} test statistics, and corresponding p -values for the 1st-neighboring and 6th-neighboring M -states respectively.

For 1st nearest neighbors M^{667} and M^{834} with $\Delta\theta = 0.007$, shown in Figure 5.3, the MKS test is only able to separate the distributions using D_{NPT} , with $p < \alpha = 0.05$. By

Figure 5.2: (a) MDS projections for M -states M^{667} and M^{834} , (b) M -state averaged D_{NPT} descriptors for M -states, and example microstructures from (c) M^{667} and (d) M^{834}

the 6th nearest neighbor, M^{787} with $\Delta\theta = 0.016$, shown in Figure 5.4, the MKS test is able to differentiate between distributions for all three descriptor methods. Figure ?? shows the resolvability limits for all three descriptor methods comparing MKS test results from the 40 nearest neighboring M -states, with the green (D_{NPT}), blue (D_{PH}), and purple (D_{ACL-2}) distributions corresponding to the span of MKS tests that failed to reject H_0 and were not able to differentiate between M -states. D_{NPT} performed the best, able to separate M^{667}

Figure 5.3: MDS projections of (a) D_{NPT} , (b) D_{PH} , and (c) D_{ACL-2} descriptors comparing 1st nearest neighbor M -states, with corresponding MKS test results shown in (d).

from all other M -states. D_{PH} performed second best, with 4/40 M -states failing to separate. D_{ACL-2} was the least resolvable, with 8/40 M -states failing to separate. An initial method in defining resolvability limits is to represent them as the $\max(\Delta\theta)$ at which the MKS test failed to separate M -states. Using this approach, the resolvability limits for D_{NPT} , D_{PH} , and D_{ACL-2} are $\Delta\theta = 0.007$, $\Delta\theta = 0.207$, and $\Delta\theta = 0.0297$ respectively. However, these results come with two caveats: firstly, that the descriptors are not necessarily equally sensitive to each individual parameter, and secondly, that the descriptors are uniformly resolvable across the \mathcal{M} -manifold. Reducing a resolvability limit down to a single $\Delta\theta$ is limiting in that depending on the direction of change, some M -states may be separable while others

Figure 5.4: MDS projections of (a) D_{NPT} , (b) D_{PH} , and (c) D_{ACL-2} descriptors comparing 6th nearest neighbor M -states, with corresponding MKS test results shown in (d).

may not. For example, D_{PH} was able to separate M -states inside the resolvability limit of $\Delta\theta = 0.207$, when that difference was largely due to a change in η parameter as opposed to κ . The same is true for D_{ACL-2} . Qualitatively, the resolvability fields for the D_{PH} and D_{ACL-2} descriptors are elongated in the κ direction, meaning that the descriptors are less sensitive, and therefore less resolvable, with respect to κ than η . This result shows the need for further statistical sensitivity and identifiability analysis in order to understand the abilities of chosen descriptors to separate effects from changing each parameter [78].

Figure 5.5: Local resolvability limits of descriptors around M^{667} .

5.2.3 Global Manifold Resolvability Assessment

Addressing the second caveat, that resolvability changes across the \mathcal{M} -manifold, a larger-scale series of MKS tests were completed. MKS tests were run comparing each of the 1000 M -states sampled in Chapter 3 to all 1000 M -states for a total of 1,000,000 individual MKS tests. From there, the resolvability limit at each M -state was determined as the $\max(\Delta\theta)$ at which the MKS test failed to separate M -states. Results for these tests for all three descriptors are shown in Figure 5.6.

The desired resolvability limit was chosen to be $\Delta\theta = 0.05$, or a 10% change in input parameters. This was chosen as the limit at which M -states can be reliably visually distinguished. D_{NPT} was the only descriptor method that largely reached this goal, with the majority of the \mathcal{M} -manifold being resolvable within a 2% change, shown in Figure 5.6b. D_{PH} , Figure 5.6c, was far less resolvable, with only small portions of the \mathcal{M} -manifold reaching that 10% threshold. Interestingly, two vertical bands of increased resolvability limits

Figure 5.6: (a) \mathcal{M} -manifold with representative microstructures, and global resolvability response surfaces for (b) D_{NPT} , (c) D_{PH} , and (d) D_{ACL-2} descriptors.

appear at the topological inflection points of the material system where the characteristic microstructures change from primary black, to highly connected, to primary white. This result is repeated in the TSNE projection of the D_{PH} descriptor in Figure 3.12 and may be attributed to the relative lack of topological features in those regions - leading to that lower resolvability between descriptors. D_{ACL-2} , in Figure 5.6d, was a middle ground between the

two other methods, with much of the \mathcal{M} -manifold achieving 10% resolvability, but reaching the same threshold of 35% resolvability as the D_{PH} descriptor, twice the maximum for D_{NPT} . Both the D_{NPT} and D_{ACL-2} descriptors have worse resolvability performance on the top half of the \mathcal{M} -manifold, for $\kappa > 0.5$. One theory for this behaviour is the relatively fewer amounts of microstructural features. As the interfacial energy parameter increases, there is a greater penalty for phase boundaries, leading to fewer, larger particles overall. This may mean that the 256×256 spatial domain is not large enough to capture a representative volume for M -states in that upper region, leading to less-descriptive representations of microstructure and worse resolvability.

5.3 Recognizing Deep Learning-Generated Microstructures

As mentioned in Chapter 4, there is a need for validation tools to ensure that the use of machine learning and deep neural networks as surrogate models for microstructure generation are creating realistic microstructure images, beyond simply visually-convincing images. If machine learning models are not able to properly generate microstructures, their use and value as a surrogate model to reduce the need for expensive simulations is decreased.

To illustrate the need for quantitative assessment of DDAE-generated microstructures, Figure 5.7 shows an example of a reference population of “Real” microstructures generated using the phase field model, and a set of three “Unknown” microstructures, generated either using the phase field model or from the DDAE network. Two of the microstructures were generated using one method, and the remaining microstructure was generated using the other method. Take some time and look at the three unknown samples to see if you can differentiate between them. See if you can determine if the lone microstructure was generated from the DDAE or PF model. Do not read ahead until you have made your guess!

Figure 5.7: Set of reference, PF-generated microstructures and three unknown samples, generated either with the PF or DDAE models.

If you recognized unknown sample 1 as different, you are correct! Unknown sample 1 was generated using the DDAE model, while unknown samples 0 and 2 were generated using the phase field model. In my experience showing these figures to a broad audience, you would be better off flipping a coin than try and recognize a microstructure image generated with the DDAE network.

In order to both assess the quality of DDAE-generated images, as well as determine the sensitivity of the stochastic microstructure descriptors established in Chapter 3, the MKS test was applied to compare populations of “Real” microstructures generated with the PF model to populations of “Fake” microstructures generated with the DDAE network. While it may be a misnomer to classify simulated microstructures as “real”, that wording is chosen here as the PF model serves as our reference for microstructures generated with physics-based constraints via the Cahn-Hilliard equation.

To complete the MKS assessment of real vs fake microstructures, three different datasets were collected across 121 M -states evenly distributed over the \mathcal{M} -manifold with 128 m -instances generated at each M -state. A “real” population was generated using the PF model, a “fake” population was generated using the DDAE network, and a “reference” population for comparing the prior two datasets was generated using the phase field model. From there, two permutation tests were completed in comparing “reference:real” and “reference:fake”, with results in the following section.

It should be noted that several image augmentations were performed to bring the DDAE-generated images onto an even playing field with the PF-generated images. First, the DDAE-generated images were histogram-matched to their corresponding PF-generated reference populations to remove the exposure effects seen in the DDAE generation process. Second, the PF-generated images were cropped to remove the periodic boundaries from the PF-generated images, as the DDAE-generated images did not have periodic boundaries. This

was necessary, as the D_{NPT} descriptor operates over periodic boundaries and would lead to an artificial discrepancy in long-range order features between the two datasets.

5.3.1 Analysis of Results

For an α threshold of 0.05, the permutation test was performed comparing “reference:real” and “reference:fake” groups, with an example of these populations and their MDS projection shown in Figure 5.8. The \widehat{MKS} test statistic between “reference:real” was 0.20, and the \widehat{MKS} test statistic between “reference:fake” was 0.47. After performing the permutation test, the p-value for “reference:real” was $p = 0.44 > \alpha$, therefore we fail to reject H_0 and cannot determine that the two groups do not come from different distributions. This is good, as the reference and real populations come from the same M -state. The p-value for “reference:fake” was $p = 0.00 < \alpha$, therefore we reject H_0 and determine that these two populations do not come from the same distribution.

The MKS test is sensitive enough to be able to differentiate between PF- and DDAE-generated populations of images. Qualitatively looking at the distribution of m -instances using the MDS visualization in Figure 5.8, this result was initially surprising. While there is no way a traditional clustering algorithm would be able to separate out the real and fake populations, the MKS test operating on the pairwise MDD values is able to use the collective information on the two populations as a whole to determine that they are distinct distributions. If performed in comparing an individual “fake” microstructure to the reference population, the MKS test is not always able to recognize fake images. However, the information on the two populations as a whole is enough to establish a meaningful distance between distributions. This can be seen in the relative shift in the center of the two populations and subsequent lateral shift in the MDS projection of data.

Figure 5.8: MDS projection of PF- and DDAE-generated populations, with the earlier unknown samples labelled in the point clouds.

Figure 5.9 shows two individual D_{NPT} descriptors for real and fake unknown samples 0 and 1, and the corresponding difference between descriptors in Figure 5.9b. From the periodic nature of the difference curve, it seems that there are slight differences in the characteristic correlation length between the two samples, leading to the separation of populations as seen in the MDS projection.

5.3.2 Application over \mathcal{M} -manifold

This analysis was repeated using the full set of 121 M -states across the \mathcal{M} -manifold. 1/121 test cases failed, meaning the DDAE has a success rate of $< 1\%$ at beating the MKS test. Figure 5.10 shows two example micrographs from the real and fake populations, as well as the MDS projection of the m -instances. In this case, the MKS test seems to have failed

Figure 5.9: (a) D_{NPT} curves for example real and fake microstructures and (b) the difference curve between D_{NPT} descriptors.

as the fake population lies wholly within the distribution of the real population. The MKS test returned a test statistic of $\widehat{MKS} = 0.267$ and a p -value of $p = 0.08 < \alpha$, therefore we reject H_0 . That being said, the results from the DDAE network are still quite impressive on the whole. DDAE-generated images are not aphysical and do not generate artifacts or impossible configurations of microstructural features that are “off-manifold” for our system. The DDAE group is much closer to its target M -state than comparing to the next-nearest neighboring M -state of PF-generated microstructures. Future work is needed to determine what differences and features the D_{NPT} and MKS tests are sensitive to, and whether or not those features are meaningful differences in terms of the microstructures themselves, or artifacts from the DDAE-generating process that can be accounted for. In close, qualitative

comparisons of DDAE to PF images, a potential differentiating feature between the two could be the boundaries between phases, where the DDAE has slightly more blurred boundaries, on the order of a handful of pixels. This difference could lead to minute changes in the D_{NPT} vectors that the MKS test is sensitive to. Another potential difference could be due to the long-range order effects of periodicity vs lack thereof in PF- and DDAE-generated datasets. While the PF-generated images are cropped to remove the periodic boundary effects before calculating the D_{NPT} descriptors, this in and of itself may be contributing to artificial separation of the populations. Further tests could be performed by updating the DDAE network to enforce periodic boundary conditions.

Figure 5.10: Example real and fake micrographs for the M -state that failed the MKS test, and the corresponding MDS projection of m -instances within those populations.

5.4 Conclusions

In conclusion, establishing quantitative measurements of material state descriptors on a metric domain allows for direct integration of statistical techniques to assess the qualities of model and descriptor uncertainty. Tools developed can be integrated with machine learning methods to assess the performance of neural networks as surrogate models for microstructure generation. The MKS test allows for resolvability assessments to be completed to determine the quality of microstructure descriptor methods and learn domain characteristics of the material manifold.

Chapter 6: Conclusions

The work in this thesis establishes a mathematical framework by which materials domain knowledge can be quantified and formalized. The construction of a \mathcal{M} -manifold allows for the navigable, bidirectional mapping between material processing conditions and the resultant structure. By establishing low-dimensional representations of data, these methods can be integrated with tools like active learning for accelerated materials discovery. This methodology can be adopted and adjusted for new problems through the careful selection of material state descriptors.

The spinodal decomposition material system was used through the phase field simulation of microstructure images. From there, stochastic, quantitative representation of the M -states were calculated, and their properties were assessed to determine their capabilities at extracting low-dimensional \mathcal{M} -manifold information. These tools were integrated with machine learning and statistical methods to further increase the usefulness of this approach.

For any dedicated reader who has made it this far, here are some final thoughts:

Contributions

The major contribution of this work is in establishing a formal approach for the understanding of material domains that comes naturally to many materials scientists. As the field of materials science expands into complex regimes, mathematical frameworks must be utilized to enable rapid, automated exploration of new domains. Minor contributions include

establishing the attributes of informative microstructure descriptors and applying manifold knowledge in collaboration with the neural network and statistics projects.

Surprises

Three major surprises stood out over the course of writing this dissertation. I initially expected microstructure descriptors to largely fall into classes of “good” and “bad”, but came to realize that each individual approach provides unique insight into the \mathcal{M} -manifold. Through careful analysis of reckless attempts at manifold recovery, each descriptor method had information to provide. A second surprise was in the degree of performance the D_{ACL-2} descriptor reached. Initially chosen as a “scapegoat” method expected to fail, the D_{ACL-2} descriptor passed both the dimensionality and invertibility tests, and provided a cohesive manifold embedding. This led me to rethink my assumptions on the need for complicated descriptors. The final surprise was the MKS test’s ability to separate M -states with incredibly small changes in parameters.

Takeaways

Ultimately, the work proposed in this dissertation was designed to be flexible and adapt to different material systems and manifold extraction techniques. I welcome any reader to take these methods, adapt them to your own needs, and argue with me as to why I was wrong. All the best.

Appendix A: Notation

\mathcal{M}	material manifold
Θ	material processing domain
θ	set of processing parameters
η	initial volume fraction
κ	interfacial energy
M^θ	“Big M ”/ M -state
\hat{M}^θ	M -state Approximation
m_i^θ	“little m ”/ m -instance
d	metric descriptor distance, MDD
D	microstructure descriptor
\bar{D}	Big M -average microstructure descriptor
D_{PH}	persistent homology descriptor
D_{NPT}	two-point function descriptor
D_{ACL}	average chord length descriptor

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